

CLOSING THE PRESERVATION LOOP

Joanna Fleming

Art Gallery NSW

Australia

Joanna.fleming@ag.nsw.gov.au

<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-7066-0256>

Lisa Mansfield

Art Gallery NSW

Australia

lisa.mansfield@ag.nsw.gov.au

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9889-4529>

Concise Summary Abstract

Preserving and displaying time-based art requires more than just the file; it demands careful documentation of the technical aspects to ensure authenticity in future presentations. Through the case studies of GROUNDLOOP (2022) by Māori artist Lisa Reihana and The Rites of When (2024) by artist Angelica Mesiti, this poster demonstrates the importance of capturing specialized details such as network mapping, color data, and audiovisual schematics, to ensure the long-term preservation of the artwork and artist's intent.

Extended Abstract

Preserving and displaying time-based art involves more than just the file; it requires detailed documentation to ensure an artwork's components, conservation, and digital preservation needs are met, while also maintaining the artist's intent.

To explore technical documentation needs for complex artworks, AGNSW used GROUNDLOOP (2022) by Māori artist Lisa Reihana as a case study. The focus was on capturing essential technical details to ensure the artwork's authenticity in future displays.

GROUNDLOOP is a single-channel video displayed on a 20m x 5m LED screen. The 520GB file runs at 25fps, with 10-bit color depth, and is encoded in NotchLC (.mov). The video runs on a Disguise server and is mapped to a custom-built NEC screen (256:63 aspect ratio) via a NovaStar controller. The work's complexity required detailed mapping of audiovisual systems, color calibration data, and network infrastructure, prompted a reassessment of existing conservation documentation.

Lessons learned were applied to 'The Rites of When' (2024) by artist Angelica Mesiti, recently exhibited in the Nelson Packer Tank gallery. The immersive installation features seven monolithic vertical screens arranged in a

circle within the 2,200-square-metre space, each with embedded speakers. Content is streamed from two Apple Mac Studios networked together running QLab. Synchronization is achieved via audio timecode, ensuring precise playback.

The intricate systems behind GROUNDLOOP and The Rites of When demonstrate that preserving media artworks is as much about understanding infrastructure as it is about safeguarding the artist's Master files. AGNSW now produce detailed signal flow diagrams as part of its suite of Conservation documentation for complex works. Capturing technical details with precision helps ensure that time-based artworks can be authentically re-experienced far into the future.

Keywords – Born Digital Content, Audiovisual Content, General Digital Preservation, Documentation.

Conference Topic – Haerenga – Journey.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Joanna Fleming is the Digital Preservation Manager at Art Gallery NSW, Australia. She is an experienced audiovisual archivist and digital preservation specialist with a demonstrated history of working in the archives, gallery and library industries. Skilled in Digital Preservation, Digital Curation, Audiovisual Preservation and Digital Film acquisition. ICAgile Certified Professional with experience working on Agile projects.

Lisa Mansfield is the Senior Time-Based Art Conservator at Art Gallery NSW, Australia, and a co-convener of the AICCM Time-based and Digital SIG. They have a special interest in software-based art, immersive media and sound.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We acknowledge the Gadigal of the Eora Nation, the traditional custodians of the Country on which the Art Gallery of New South Wales stands.

First presented at BDCAM 2025, this poster has been updated with lessons learned and an additional case study for IPRES 2025.

